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Which forests could be protected by corporate zero deforestation commitments? A spatial assessment

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Abstract

The production of palm oil, soy, beef and timber are key drivers of global forest loss. For this reason, over 470 companies involved in the production, processing or distribution of these commodities have issued commitments to eliminate or reduce deforestation from their supply chains. However, the effectiveness of these commitments is uncertain since there is considerable variation in ambition and scope and there are no globally agreed definitions of what constitutes a forest. Many commitments identify high conservation value forests (HCVFs), high carbon stock forests (HCSFs) and forests on tropical peatland as priority areas for conservation. This allows for mapping of the global extent of forest areas classified as such, to achieve an assessment of the area that may be at reduced risk of development if companies comply with their zero deforestation commitments. Depending on the criteria used, the results indicate that between 34% and 74% of global forests qualify as either HCVF, HCSF or forests on tropical peatland. However, we found that the total extent of these forest areas varies widely depending on the choice of forest map. Within forests which were not designated as HCVF, HCSF or forests on tropical peatland, there is substantial overlap with areas that are highly suitable for agricultural development. Since these areas are unlikely to be protected by zero-deforestation commitments, they may be subject to increased pressure resulting from leakage of areas designated as HCVF, HCSF and tropical peatland forests. Considerable uncertainties around future outcomes remain, since only a proportion of the global market is currently covered by corporate commitments. Further work is needed to map the synergies between corporate commitments and government policies on land use. In addition, standardized criteria for delineating forests covered by the commitments are recommended.

1. Introduction

Commodity-driven deforestation is a major driver of global forest loss accounting for approximately 27% of global forest loss (Curtis *et al* 2018). Recognizing this, many multinationals sourcing deforestation-risk commodities have adopted goals to eliminate or reduce deforestation from their supply chains (Lambin *et al* 2018). These zero-deforestation commitments (ZDCs) typically focus on the four agricultural commodities most strongly associated with tropical deforestation: beef, palm oil, soy, paper and pulp (Henders *et al* 2015, Newton and Benzeev 2018).

In recent years, the number of companies adopting ZDCs has grown rapidly to at least 484, representing an unknown market share (Donofrio *et al* 2019).

However, the effectiveness of ZDCs is uncertain since there is considerable variation in ambition and scope (Jopke and Schoneveld 2018, Taylor and Streck 2018). In addition, there are no globally agreed definitions of what constitutes a forest; variations arise from consideration of tree density, tree height, ecological properties etc (Chazdon *et al* 2016). The choice of forest definition influences estimates of forest areas globally and therefore deforestation estimates. As an example, Romijn *et al* (2013) demonstrated the total

area estimated to have been deforested between 2000 and 2009 in Indonesia increased by 27% when using Indonesia's national forest definition instead of the Food Agricultural Organization (FAO) definition.

Many companies identify high conservation value forests (HCVFs) (Brown *et al* 2013) and high carbon stock forests (HCSFs) (Rosoman *et al* 2017) as priority areas for conservation within their ZDCs. HCVFs are defined as forests of outstanding biological, ecological, social or cultural significance and divided into six categories: four focus on biodiversity, habitat and ecosystem conservation, and a further two on community needs and cultural values (Brown *et al* 2013). HCSFs are defined by a practical, field-tested methodology—the high carbon stock approach (HCSA)—that prioritizes forests for conservation based on their above-ground biomass (AGB) carbon, while respecting communities' rights to their lands and typically integrating the findings of an HCV assessment (Rosoman *et al* 2017). In addition, many companies have also committed to the protection of forest on tropical peatlands (Newton and Benzev 2018). The adoption of these so-called 'No Deforestation, No Peat and No Exploitation' (NDPE) commitments has been limited to the oil palm sector in Southeast Asia where 74% of the palm oil refining capacity is now covered by such commitments (Steinweg *et al* 2017). Recently, the Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) integrated the HCSA into its Principles and Criteria (RSPO 2018). Discussions are ongoing as to whether the HCSA approach should also be included by other standard bodies, including the Roundtable on Responsible Soy (RTRS), the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) and the United Nations Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and forest Degradation (REDD+) Programme (Cheyns *et al* 2019).

Although commitments to protect HCVF and HCSFs have been recognized as potentially effective approaches for implementing a ZDC (Garrett *et al* 2019), the spatial extent of HCVFs and HCSFs is unknown (Pirker *et al* 2016, Carlson *et al* 2018). Both approaches were developed for local, case-by-case application requiring on-the-ground field visits and stakeholder consultation. As a result, mapping has been conducted mainly at the local scale, leaving unclear what the global coverage of the ZDCs is. In addition, concerns around deforestation extend to the development of new production areas on forests and other biomes which fall outside of the HCVF and HCSF classifications—a phenomenon often referred to as activity leakage (Meyfroidt *et al* 2018, Bastos Lima *et al* 2019). Therefore, the primary objective of this paper is to make an estimate of the global land area that could be classified as HCVF, HCSF or forest on tropical peatland, and hence at reduced risk of development if companies comply with their ZDCs. A secondary objective is to identify the remaining forest

areas that are at risk of conversion due to agricultural development or forestry.

2. Methodology

A stepwise approach was adopted to estimate the global forested land area that can be classified as HCVF, HCSF or forest on tropical peatlands. First, a forest reference map for the current situation was created (section 2.1.1). Then, HCVFs (section 2.1.2), HCSFs (section 2.1.3) and tropical peatland forests (section 2.1.3) were identified separately by matching a variety of data sources to the official definitions and descriptions listed in the HCV guidelines and HCSA toolkit.

The forested areas that were not classified as HCVF, HCSF or tropical peatland forest were intersected with several maps displaying agricultural suitability for the four main deforestation-risk commodities, market accessibility, future land use change projections and areas where commodity-driven deforestation and forestry are considered the main driver of forest loss (sections 2.2.1–2.2.3).

2.1. Estimating the global extent of HCVF, HCSF and forests on tropical peatland in 2017

2.1.1. Mapping forest areas.

To create a forest reference map for the current situation, the binary forest map from (Schulze *et al* 2019) was used. This 1 km² resolution map is based on a hybrid forest map created by (Schepaschenko *et al* 2015) and represents the year 2000, calibrated with the most recent FAO statistics. We modified the forest extent to represent the year 2017 using 1 km² raster data on tree cover gain (2000–2012) and tree cover loss (2000–2017) from (Hansen *et al* 2013, 2019), accessed through Google Earth Engine. Recognising that tree cover loss data from Hansen *et al* do not distinguish between temporary loss and permanent conversion (Curtis *et al* 2018) and that tree cover gain data include plantation forests and herbaceous crops (Tropek *et al* 2014), we tested the sensitivity of the mapped forest area using both the original and our updated Schulze map. In addition, we tested the sensitivity of mapped forest areas arising from the choice of forest map by using nine alternative global forest maps (table 1). Finally, all spatial data were converted to an equal-area Eckert IV projection as advocated in (Šavrič *et al* 2015).

2.1.2. Mapping HCV forests.

We used the HCV guidelines (Brown *et al* 2013) to identify and map HCVFs using 12 distinct indicators that together cover the full range of HCV categories, as shown in table 1 (see also table 1 available online at stacks.iop.org/ERL/15/064021/mmedia of the supplementary material for an extended ver-

Table 1. List of indicators and data sources to identify HCSE, HCVF and forest on tropical peatlands.

	Indicator	Thresholds	Data sources
Forest extent 2017	Hybrid forest map for the year 2000 that integrates eight different forest products, validated with crowdsourced data, consistent with FAO statistics, updated to the year 2017 based on remotely sensed data of tree cover loss and gain between 2000–2017. As a sensitivity analysis, nine different forest maps are considered. Percentage tree-cover maps from (Hansen <i>et al</i> 2019) and (Sexton <i>et al</i> 2013) were converted to binary forest maps (forest/no forests) by applying a 10% and 30% threshold, following the official forest definitions of the (FAO 2012) and the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC 2006), respectively.		Schulze <i>et al</i> 2019 and Hansen <i>et al</i> 2019 Sensitivity analysis: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bartholomé and Belward 2005 • Bontemps <i>et al</i> 2016 • Buchhorn <i>et al</i> 2019 • Hansen <i>et al</i> 2019 (two maps with 10% and 30% canopy cover threshold) • Schaaf and Wang 2015 • Sexton <i>et al</i> 2013 (two maps with 10% and 30% canopy cover threshold) • Shimada <i>et al</i> 2014, 2019 • Hoffman <i>et al</i> 2016
High conservation value	HCV 1 Species diversity	Biodiversity Hotspots Key Biodiversity Areas Nationally Designated Protected Areas	BirdLife International 2018 UNEP-WCMC and IUCN 2018
	HCV 2 Landscape-level ecosystems and mosaics and Intact Forest Landscapes	Intact Forest Landscapes	Potapov <i>et al</i> 2017, 2008
	HCV 3 Ecosystems and habitats	Areas of high forest biodiversity significance	Hill <i>et al</i> 2019
	HCV 4 Ecosystem services	Areas of high overlap of nature's contributions and people's needs in terms of coastal risk reduction, crop pollination, erosion protection, reduction of flood risk, water quality and water supply.	Chaplin-Kramer <i>et al</i> 2019, Stehfest <i>et al</i> 2014 and CIESIN 2018
	HCV 5 Community needs	Presence of Indigenous Community	Garnett <i>et al</i> 2018
	HCV 6 Cultural values	UNESCO World Heritage Sites (part of Nationally Designated Protected Areas)	UNEP-WCMC and IUCN 2018
High carbon stock	Above-ground biomass ($t\ C\ ha^{-1}$) within tropical forest areas.	75 (Low Density Forest) 35 (Young Regenerating Forest)	Santoro and Cartus 2019 Sensitivity analysis: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avitabile <i>et al</i> 2016 • Baccini <i>et al</i> 2012
Pan-tropical peatlands	Presence of peatland in the tropics.	Pan-tropical soils having at least 30 cm of decomposed or semi decomposed organic material with at least 50% of organic matter.	Gumbricht <i>et al</i> 2017

sion of this list, including the official definition of each HCV category and the rationale for selecting each indicator). To harmonize the different datasets,

all indicators were converted to a 1 km² resolution. We used three different thresholds to classify HCVFs, defined as forest areas containing at least one, two, or

three HCV categories. The different levels of coverage were used to represent the uncertainty in the final HCVE classification and illustrate the sensitivity of the mapped spatial extent to the indicator selection. We assumed that areas with multiple overlapping categories are more likely to qualify as HCVE.

2.1.3. Mapping HCS forests.

According to the HCS Toolkit Version 2.0 (Rosoman *et al* 2017), potential HCSF can be identified based on an above-ground biomass (AGB) threshold of 35 t C ha⁻¹. Although some potential HCSF may still be released for development, all tropical forests containing more than 75 t C ha⁻¹ are generally designated as HCSF (Rosoman *et al* 2017). We used both thresholds to indicate the range of uncertainty in the classification of HCSF and its mapped spatial extent. Above ground biomass data from (Santoro and Cartus 2019), representing the year 2017, were resampled from a resolution of 1 ha to a resolution of 1 km² using the majority resampling approach. For sensitivity analyses, two alternative AGB carbon maps were considered (see table 1). Since the HCS approach is not applicable for forests outside the tropics (Rosoman *et al* 2017), these were not classified as HCS.

2.1.4. Mapping forests on tropical peatland.

Tropical peatland forests were mapped using data on the pan-tropical extent of peatlands in 2011 from (Gumbricht *et al* 2017).

2.2. Evaluating forests at risk of agricultural development

We evaluated the deforestation risk of forest areas not designated as HCVE, HCSF or tropical peatland. Forests designated as HCV or HCS were for this analysis defined as forests with at least two overlapping HCVE categories or at least 75 t C ha⁻¹ if located in the tropics (section 2.1). The risk of potential future conversion of forest was assessed using three alternative approaches to account for the uncertainty in future development: (1) by identifying and overlaying suitable and accessible expansion areas for the 4 main deforestation-risk commodities (section 2.2.1), (2) by using integrated assessment model predictions (section 2.2.2), and (3) by masking areas where commodity-driven deforestation and forestry are considered the main drivers of forest loss (section 2.2.3).

2.2.1. Overlap with suitable and accessible expansion areas for the 4 deforestation-risk commodities.

Data on agro-ecological suitability for oil palm, soybean and pasture were sourced from the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis/Food and Agriculture Organization (2012) and Van Velthuizen *et al* (2007), and resampled to a resolution of 1 km² using the majority resampling approach (a list of all data

sources can be found in table 2 of the supplementary material). These suitability maps include eight different suitability classes for current agricultural or pastoral production areas as well as those which could be developed for future production. To identify suitable areas for forestry, a similar suitability map for potential production forests was made by classifying a continuous suitability map from (Schulze *et al* 2019) into eight suitability classes. For each commodity, potential areas for expansion were identified by excluding areas already under production. For oil palm, soybean and pasture, only the estimated fraction of any given grid cell currently under cultivation was known (Ramankutty *et al* 2010, International Food Policy Research Institute 2019). We therefore excluded grid cells where cropland or pastureland already extend over more than 50% of the area (a sensitivity analysis towards this assumption is provided in the supplementary material). Grid cells comprising urban land were also excluded, using data from (Schneider *et al* 2003). Forest areas outside the HCV, HCS and tropical peatland areas overlapping with suitable expansion areas were assumed to be at risk of conversion.

As inaccessible lands may face lower risk of development (Busch and Ferretti-Gallon 2017), we refined the analysis by mapping the joint distribution of market accessibility and agricultural suitability for forests falling outside the HCV, HCS and tropical peatland areas. Data from (Weiss *et al* 2018) on travel time to the closest port or the closest city with at least 50 000 inhabitants—resampled to a resolution of 1 km² using bilinear interpolation—were used as a proxy for market accessibility. To obtain an overall measure of agricultural suitability for the 4 commodities, a raster layer was created indicating, for each grid cell, the highest overall suitability class of the 4 suitability layers (a separate map for each of the 4 commodities is presented in the supplementary material).

2.2.2. Overlap with land use projections.

An alternative estimate of the conversion risk placed on areas falling beyond the HCVE, HCSF and tropical peatland forests classifications was derived using spatially explicit land use projections of cropland and pastureland expansion at 5 arc minutes resolution from the Integrated Model to Assess the Global Environment (IMAGE) 3.0 model (Doelman *et al* 2018). These projections were made for the period 2020–2030 and based on the second Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP2) scenario (a ‘middle-of-the-road’ scenario for future climate mitigation action) (O’Neill *et al* 2014). Forest areas that were not classified as HCVE, HCSF or tropical peatland forest and were found to overlap areas of projected cropland or pastureland expansion were considered to be at additional risk of development.

Table 2. Estimated total extent of high conservation value forests, high carbon stock forests and tropical peatland forests. High carbon stock estimates are based on (Santoro and Cartus 2019), while the parentheses behind the high carbon Stock estimates indicate the lower and upper range using two alternative above-ground biomass maps (i.e. Avitabile *et al* (2016) and Baccini *et al* (2012)).

Geographic scope	Type of forest	Million km ²	% total forest area
Global	High conservation value		
	≥1 category	25.67	65%
	≥2 categories	10.61	27%
	≥3 categories	2.56	7%
Tropical	High conservation value		
	≥1 category	13.59	73%
	≥2 categories	7.09	38%
	≥3 categories	2.17	12%
	High carbon stock		
	≥35 t C ha ⁻¹	14.89 (13.53–17.00)	80% (73%–91%)
	≥75 t C ha ⁻¹	12.75 (12.30–15.26)	68% (66%–82%)
Peatland forests	0.62	3%	

2.2.3. Overlap with areas where commodity-driven deforestation and forestry are dominant drivers of forest loss.

Finally, we assessed the overlap between forests not classified as HCS, HCV or tropical peatland and areas where forestry and commodity-driven deforestation are classed as the main drivers of forest loss. Data on the drivers of forest loss at 10 km² resolution were sourced from Curtis *et al* (2018). This provides an indication of the forest areas that are at additional risk of development, assuming these forests will indeed be subject to forestry or commodity-driven deforestation.

3. Results

3.1. The estimated extent of HCVF, HCSF and forests on tropical peatland in 2017

Based on the updated Schulze *et al* map for the year 2017, the global forest area amounts to 39.4 million km² (this compares with an area of 40.3 million km² if the Schulze *et al* map is not updated). Figure 1 shows the variation in the spatial extent of HCVF and HCSF, depending on the stringency of the criteria. The total extent of HCVF and HCSF combined comprises between 34% and 74% of global forests, of which between 28% and 34% has already been designated as protected area (UNEP-WCMC 2018). The global extent of HCVF alone encompasses between 7% and 65% of global forests (table 2), with indigenous lands accounting for the largest part of potential HCVF (i.e. 43% of all potential HCVF, see figure 1 of the supplementary material).

Since HCSFs are by definition limited to the tropical zone, the total extent is much smaller than the extent of HCVF and varies in the range of 31%–43% of global forests, which equates to 66%–91% of all tropical forests, depending on the choice of AGB map and whether an AGB threshold of 35 or 75 t C ha⁻¹ is applied. Within the tropical zone, there is an overlap between HCVF and HCSF, with the percentage of total tropical forest for which the

two classifications converge—measured by the Jaccard Similarity Index (Intersection over Union)—varying between 14% and 67%, depending on both the AGB threshold and minimum number of overlapping HCV categories. Tropical peatland forests comprise 3% of all tropical forests, of which between 82% and 98% overlap with HCVFs and HCSFs.

At a regional or country level, the large sensitivity of the extent of HCVF and HCSF to the choice of criteria can lead to dramatic differences (see figures 2 and 3 of the supplementary material). For example, the total extent of HCVF, HCSF and tropical peatland forest in Sub-Saharan Africa varies in the range of 51%–84% of all forests.

To test how sensitive the results are to the choice of forest map, figure 2 shows the variation in the extent of HCVF, HCSF and tropical peatland forest when different forest maps are considered. Forests designated as HCVF or HCSF are here defined as forests containing at least two overlapping HCVF categories or exceeding the AGB threshold of 75 t C ha⁻¹. To account for the uncertainty in the extent of HCSF and HCVF, the error bars in figure 2 denote the upper and lower range of the extent of HCSF, HCVF and tropical peatland forest using the full range of criteria shown in figure 1 (see table 3 of the supplementary material for a detailed comparison of the 10 forest maps based on the Jaccard Similarity index). The total extent of forests designated as HCVF, HCSF or tropical peatland depends to a large extent on the choice of forest map and varies in the range of 11–40 million km², notably because large areas considered forest by some maps are classified as closed shrublands or woody savannahs by others.

3.2. Forest at risk of agricultural development

Figure 3 shows the extent to which potential suitable expansion areas for the 4 deforestation-risk commodities overlap with forest areas and forest areas designated as HCVF, HCSF or tropical peatland, based on different land suitability thresholds. Depending on the suitability classes included, 39%–92% of the

areas suitable for forestry expansion and 57%–80% of the areas suitable for the expansion of oil palm plantations overlap with forests designated as HCVF, HCSF or tropical peatland. The total forest area outside HCVFs, HCSFs and tropical peatland forests that is suitable for forestry ranges between 0.57 to 17.81 million km², while the area suitable for oil palm plantations ranges between 0.30 and 6.82 million km². Potential suitable expansion areas for pasturelands and soybean fields are much more abundant resulting in a lower percentage overlap with forests (36%–52% and 6%–36%, respectively). Still, given their overall larger extent, the total forest area not covered by HCVFs, HCSFs and peatland forests is as high as

19.73 million km² for pastureland and 10.61 million km² for soybean fields.

To assess where pressures from forestry and agricultural expansion are especially high, figure 4 displays the joint distribution of market accessibility—classified into eight octiles—and agricultural suitability, based on the highest land suitability class for the four commodities (see figure 5 of the supplementary material for four separate maps per commodity). Forests not designated as HCVF, HCSF or tropical peatland forest with high market accessibility and agricultural suitability tend to be clustered in the Eastern United States, Central Europe, East China, the Gran Chaco in Latin America and near

the Swahili Coast in Sub-Saharan Africa (see figures 6(a)–(c) of the supplementary material for three zoom maps of Latin America, Sub-Saharan Africa and Southeast Asia; the three main global deforestation regions (FAO 2018)). Around 36% of these forest areas with the highest market accessibility and agricultural suitability are estimated to be already

used as production forests, based on data from (Schulze *et al* 2019).

These results merely indicate risk based on agro-ecological suitability and accessibility and do not account for projected changes in land use linked to anticipated growth in demand, population density and market accessibility. Projections from the IMAGE

3.0 model for crop and pasture expansion between 2020 and 2030, reflect drivers of land use change. These projections indicate that 38% of the total forest area not designated as HCVF, HCSF or tropical peatland forest, may be subject to land use change for agricultural production. Assuming these predictions provide a reasonable indication of the location of future production for the four deforestation-risk commodities, the total forest area at risk of becoming converted to oil palm plantations, soybean fields or pastureland becomes much smaller—especially in the temperate zone—and decreases on average by 59% (see figure 7 of the supplementary material). It is important to note though that these estimates do not account for potential leakage effects from protecting HCVEs, HCSFs and tropical peatland forests.

Alternatively, focussing only on areas where commodity-driven deforestation or forestry is considered the main driver of forest loss, the total forest area at risk amounts to 56% of the total forest area not classified as HCVE, HCSF or tropical peatland forest, of which 17% overlaps with areas where commodity-driven deforestation is considered the main driver of forest loss.

4. Discussion and conclusions

This study provides a first approximation of the global forest area that may be covered by corporate zero deforestation commitments (ZDCs), defined on the basis of three commonly used criteria: protection of high conservation value forests (HCVF), high carbon stock forests (HCSF) and tropical peatland forests. The results show that between 34% and 74% of

all forests may classify as HCVE, HCSF or peatland forest. This large range indicates the level of uncertainty in the extent of forest that could be at reduced risk of development if these commitments were fully adopted. However, given that market coverage of the corporate commitments is less than 100%, the protected area will be much smaller in reality and deforestation can move to supply chains falling beyond the scope of the corporate commitments (Garrett *et al* 2019). Moreover, even in case of full uptake, legally protected forest accounts for only 28%–34% of the forest area that we identified as meeting our ZDC criteria.

In comparison with individual site-based local assessments conducted by companies, our global assessment of the spatial coverage of HCVE and HCSF is likely to identify some different areas for conservation. First and foremost, this is because the methods used to identify HCVEs and HCSFs were developed for local assessments requiring extensive field work and free, prior and informed consent from local communities, meaning they are not easily applied at larger scales (i.e. the 1 km² resolution we use) (Lake *et al* 2016, Pirker *et al* 2016). In addition, many of the criteria documented in the HCV guidelines contain ambiguous and subjective terms that depend on individual assessors' discretion. This has led to an inconsistency between various local HCV assessments (Senior *et al* 2015), meaning that there is no consensus on what potential HCV indicators are most appropriate. There are also no spatial data sets available on areas already designated as HCVE and HCSF (Carlson *et al* 2018, HCSA Steering Group 2019) to enable validation. Finally, all indicators used to

approximate the spatial extent of HCVE and HCSF had to be resampled to a resolution of 1 km², which inevitably leads to some loss of spatial detail (Zhu *et al* 2017). To reduce uncertainty in the spatial extent of forest protected under the corporate commitments, standardized criteria for delineating forests and defining areas of HCVE and HCSF at the global scale and across tropical and temperate forests are recommended. In addition, advances in remote sensing and biodiversity mapping should be exploited to produce more accurate and up-to-date indicators of HCVEs and HCSFs.

Despite these uncertainties, our results are relatively consistent with previous attempts to map HCVE and HCSF areas at larger scales. For example, Miranda *et al* (2003) estimated that 37% of all areas designated as forest according to our reference map are potentially HCVE, which compares with our estimate of 27% (for two overlapping HCVE categories), and Austin *et al* (2017) estimated the total extent of HCSF in Gabon to be between 80% and 87% of Gabon's land, which compares with our estimate of 83% (regardless of the choice of carbon threshold).

Our analysis has also shown that the extent of HCVE, HCSF and tropical peatland forests is contingent on the choice of forest map, resulting in a range from 11 to 40 million km² according to the criteria specified in figure 2. This finding adds to a growing body of literature showing that the definition of forest significantly impacts estimates of forest cover and forest cover change (Chazdon *et al* 2016, Sexton *et al* 2016, Mermoz *et al* 2018). The lack of a well-agreed forest definition led nine environmental and social NGOs to launch the Accountability Framework initiative in 2016; a framework that has been developed to provide companies with detailed guidance to implement their commitments and standardize definitions of forest, deforestation, and related terms (Weber and Partzsch 2018). Greater consensus on forest classification is needed to reduce the uncertainty in the area covered by the corporate commitments and facilitate more effective monitoring (Lyons-White and Knight 2018).

Even if the ZDCs are fully implemented across all commodity markets, some of the environmental and social benefits associated with the protection of HCVE, HCSF and tropical peatland forest may be undermined if agricultural expansion is displaced to forests that are not covered, hence resulting in activity leakage (Meyfroidt *et al* 2018, Bastos Lima *et al* 2019). Using data on land suitability for the four main deforestation-risk commodities, we have shown here that many forest areas not designated as HCVE, HCSF or tropical peatland forest are highly suitable for the production of these commodities, indicating an increased potential risk of development due to ZDCs. Hence, with a growing world demand for all four commodities (Corley 2009, Masuda and Goldsmith 2009, Thornton 2010, Johnston 2016), pressures on

potential expansion areas will likely increase and could possibly come at the expense of forests or other biomes, including savannahs and grasslands, not designated as HCVE, HCSF or tropical peatland forest, in particular when market accessibility is high (Atmadja and Verchot 2012). In addition, pressures may be higher at local scales due to imperfect substitution between commodities originating from different sources (Hertel 2018). However, the total area at risk of development may be much smaller when accounting for future land use change scenarios or historic trends in commodity-driven deforestation or forestry.

It should be noted, though, that there are many factors that we have not been able to consider in our assessment of the areas at risk of future agricultural development. For example, there are a range of interacting socio-economic factors—including mobility of capital and labour, easy access to credit and differences in price and terms (Atmadja and Verchot 2012)—policy and governance factors (Fernandes *et al* 2015) as well as crop-to-crop cascade effects (Lambin and Meyfroidt 2011), which are all likely to affect future land use outcomes. Further work to map synergies between corporate commitments and government policies influencing land use outcomes is recommended. This will help to refine estimates of the potential effectiveness of national and supply chain governance levers for halting deforestation and for the identification of complementary strategies which may accelerate efforts towards zero deforestation.

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Data availability

Data on current production forests and forestry suitability estimates can be obtained from Katharina

Schulze. Data on indigenous communities and forest biodiversity significance are available from Stephen T Garnett and Samantha Hill. The other data that support the findings of this study are available upon request from the corresponding author.

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